

FACTORS IN THE FORMATION OF CULTURAL VALUES IN FUTURE ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS

Ibrokhimova S.N

sarvinozibroximova0@gmail.com

Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

*The teacher of department "Foreign languages accurate and natural
directions"*

Abstract: This article talks about how to form, improve and develop cultural values among English language teachers today. Because honoring spiritual and cultural values is one of the urgent issues of today.

Key words: Culture, cultural values, worldview, perfect person, pedagogical methods, new modern methods, psychology, psychological activity.

Today, we would not be mistaken if we say that modern approaches to improving the efficiency and quality of higher education in New Uzbekistan, modernizing its content, modernizing the educational system, raising it to the level of modern requirements, creating a new system of national personnel training, and educating a young generation with full potential are aimed at realizing the priority. Taking into account the attitude of young people to spiritual and cultural values in the new Uzbekistan, President Sh.M. Mirziyoev's " Measures to bring up young people to be spiritually, morally and physically perfect, and to raise the quality of their education system to a new level" ” decision No. PD-3907 dated August 14, 2018. It is important to note that all the issues highlighted in this decision are relevant. In particular, the decision states the following: "to improve the legal culture of young people, to prevent the commission of offenses and crimes among them; educating selfless and patriotic young people with high morale, a firm life position, and a broad outlook; protecting young people from the influence of foreign ideas, educating them in the spirit of loyalty to national and universal values, religious tolerance and inter- ethnic harmony ; it is necessary to pay special attention to

education, formation of their desire to acquire knowledge and self-improvement [2]”. Based on the above-mentioned points, it is necessary to convey to today's youth that the place of pedagogy is high in the worldview, spiritual and cultural education of young people. Currently, the connection of pedagogy with the science of psychology, especially the solution of pedagogical problems by relying on certain psychological aspects of the young people being educated, is not being paid attention to. Correct understanding of this aspect will surely help the future generation a lot. Because without taking into account the age characteristics of each pupil, it will be a bit incomprehensible to implement a person-oriented education consisting of his intellectual development and spiritual culture education, various activities and self-awareness. In this matter, the psychophysiological development of students, including the methods and technologies of pedagogical activity, consists of the ideas of psychological development, the main types of activity, and the main pedagogical ideas. Each of these factors has its specific meaning depending on the age aspect of the subject being studied.

For example, psychophysiological characteristics study the biological aspects of the formation and development of a person. The student's ability to participate in this or that type of activity is manifested in his physical development qualities, individual-psychological identity, communication capabilities, creativity, compliance with social norms and micro-social rules in his behavior, and the ability to be a real member of his group or team.

In the most basic types of activity, the pupil's age, typological characteristics, and priority motives of activity are reflected . Favorable opportunities for the development of activity, conditions, situations of inhibition, factors hindering motivation and ways of their prevention are determined and the work is done accordingly.

The main pedagogical ideas are required to reflect the leading strategic goal aimed at the implementation of the main types of student or team activities in the

organization of the pedagogical process. Priority directions and technologies of pedagogical activity should be structured in such a way that it should be relatively easier to apply the main pedagogical ideas to the activity of the student-youth team. It takes into account the laws of the educational process, the method, form, tools, methods of organizing communication, pedagogical activity; analysis results, the main trends of individual and team development are determined and the components of age characteristics are determined. In this regard, it is considered very important to create technologies that create creative possibilities not only of students, but also of teachers. These technologies require a unique approach to acquiring a system of knowledge based on the student's life experiences.

Today, attention is paid to these specific features in the formation of the general cultural worldview and cultural values of students and young people.

These factors depend on the effective implementation of the educational process in higher education institutions. But this problem is little researched in the psychology of higher education, and it requires studying the psychological characteristics of students. The main feature of this period is the rapid emergence of social maturity. Because it is not difficult to learn from everyday life that during the student period, every young person is ready to perform various tasks in social life along with learning.

It would be appropriate to call these tasks such as building a family, raising children, and working. The main criteria of this process are activity in work, sense of responsibility in front of laws, feeling of preparation for specialization, volition, feeling of duty to have a family, readiness for leadership activities, ability to distribute free time and organize it in the right way. Scientists such as M.G. Davletshin [3], V. Karimova and R. Sunnatova [4] have pointed out that students have difficulty in the educational process, problems in finding a way out of difficult situations, youth strength, will, They attach great importance to the improvement of the qualities of independence, initiative, ingenuity, prudence with their intelligence,

as well as to the strengthening of interest in social situations, reality, moral rules, and the desire to understand them.

In conclusion, it is impossible to ensure the interrelationship of psychology and pedagogy in the education of a perfect person, without taking into account the young characteristics and intellectual development of each student and his spiritual culture. In this regard, the psycho-physiological development of students, including the directions and technologies of pedagogical activity, and the main types of activity in this development require constant cooperation with the conditions in the institution.

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